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The Art and Skill of Translation

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***Abstract:** This article talks about the art of translation and the skill, creative abilities of the translator, as well as the re-creation of the translator's original as a work of art in form and content according to modern translation requirements, national and personal approach, and expression of his skills. In the process of translation, the ability to choose the right term, work on linguistic and grammatical errors, observation, scientific-critical study, along with this, information about limits and norms are described.*

***Key words:** art of translation, translator skills, information technology, linguistic, grammatical and stylistic errors.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, developments in information technology and the creation of specialized translation tools have reduced the demand for human translators, leading to a decline in the quality of translation. This situation primarily indicates the existence of certain challenges associated with the distinction between machine translation and human translation.

The progress of the 21st century has had a significant impact on research into natural languages related to the advancement of computer technology, particularly in the field of machine translation. However, due to the rapid growth of international relations and the integration of modern economies, there is an increasing need for professional translators with expertise in translating scientific and technical texts across various industries.

In such cases, translators are expected to possess a high level of proficiency and knowledge, including a broad vocabulary and an understanding of technical terms. Translators must continually update their vocabulary and familiarize themselves with new terminology in order to ensure accurate and effective translations.

In addition, when translating scientific and technical texts, the translator should have skills such as comparing terms with other relevant terms and conducting analysis. A qualified translator also relies on the theoretical and practical knowledge acquired from scientific disciplines in their work.

METHODOLOGY AND ANALYZING THE LITERATURE

Translation is an art form, and the translator is a creative professional. Why is translation considered an art? It is because, in order for the reader of a translated text to understand the message of the original text, the translator must be able to convey the meaning and intent of the source language into the target language with precision and accuracy. This requires not only a deep understanding of both languages, but also a sensitivity to the cultural and emotional nuances of each.

Translation is not merely a matter of transferring words from one language to another; it is also about capturing the essence and spirit of the original work. A successful translation should not only be accurate, but also evoke similar emotions and sensations in the reader as the original did. This is why translation is considered an art form - it requires creativity, skill, and a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures.

The art of translation, in conjunction with translation, permeates into the original text and its context, and reflects the principles, rules, and standards. Therefore, the book by journalist Rana Zaripova, "The Art of Translation and the Skill of a Translator," discusses the art of translation and skills of a professional translator, exploring the characteristics of translating works by two prominent figures in Ukrainian literature, Les Ukrainka and Oles'a Gonchar.

The art of translating continues to be essential in the advancement of global culture, and interest in this field has been steadily increasing. Indeed, translation is a process that aims to transfer the essence of one language into another, thereby gaining the admiration of readers.

The translator should be familiar with the level of development, history, and meaning of the source language, as this enhances the translator's abilities in terms of creativity and knowledge. In the course of their translation, translators are required to adhere to certain linguistic, grammatical, and stylistic guidelines. If the translator encounters terminological challenges that they are unable to resolve on their own, they may conduct their own research.

RESULTS

Translation is not a simple copying process, but a creative and challenging task for the translator. The translator adds their own artistic touch to each line they translate, while at the same time the writer artistically conveys the observations they have gained from life experiences. Through this process, the translator revisits the original text using a different language.

The success of a translation depends on the deep knowledge, wide horizons, and extensive life experience of the translator. These factors ensure that the translated text is accurate and well-crafted.

A.V. Fedorov, a Russian linguist, proposed the concept of general translation theory. This concept emphasizes that any high-quality translation should begin with a philological analysis of the linguistic foundation of the text and end with artistic or scientific editing.

DISCUSSION

During the translation process, translators might encounter various expressions, words and, as scientists state, it is impossible to avoid disagreements regarding phrases in translations. When the words used in translations do not usually correspond to the original text, it is important to pay attention

to their meaning, as the goal is to accurately convey the intended meaning. For instance, the English idiom "when pigs fly" is translated into Uzbek as "when the camel touches the ground". Additionally, abstract verbs are commonly used in the scientific style of writing in English.

In English: Our planet is wrapped in a mass of gases.

In Uzbek: Bizning sayyoramiz gazlar bilan o'ralgan.

Translation has separate guidelines for artistic works and distinct rules for grammar and vocabulary. In art history, for example, a translator should not only fully comprehend translation issues but also possess certain creative abilities. The significance and role of intangible elements, such as talent and inspiration, in reinterpreting an artwork into a target language are invaluable. In particular, poetic translations present a challenge when it comes to creating rhyme.

In Uzbek: Jondin seni ko'p sevarman, ey umri aziz,

Sondin seni ko'p sevarman, ey umri aziz.

In English: I love you more than my soul, oh, my dear,

I love you more than all numbers, oh, my dear.

it would be challenging to maintain consistent rhyme throughout the poem. Alternatively, while maintaining the rhyme scheme, there is the question of whether the full transfer of the emotions conveyed in the original text can be achieved in the translated version.

SUMMARY

In the process of translation, translators face numerous practical challenges. To enhance the art of translation, principles for expanding the creative approach have been outlined. The original text of a translation by a translator focuses on the correspondence, accuracy, and mutual compatibility of all specific and general requirements for the text, as well as its genre and content. A translator should be purposeful, possess sufficient knowledge in each relevant field, and possess the skills necessary to provide numerous benefits for the translation process.

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